

THE INFLUENCE OF CORONAVIRUS ON THE HIGHER EDUCATION SERVICES (CASE STUDY OF ISRAEL & MOLDOVA)

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***Abstract:** The trends of growing demand among learners in higher education systems leading for improved accessibility and convenience, lower costs, and direct application of content to work settings in the institutes. This radically changing the local and international environment for higher education system. The new phenomenon of using technical methods is demand the competition between the organization. If we look at the United States and globally (other countries), in this rapidly changing environment, which is increasingly based within the context of a global and knowledge-based economy and competition between higher education systems. The author found that higher education organizational in Israel and Moldova have changes, and new developments are being fueled by accelerating advances. The author will describe the local situation and the trends in the Israeli & Moldavian higher education system.*

***Key Words:** Competition, Education Services System, Excellence Organization, Higher Education.*

INFLUENȚA CORONAVIRUSULUI ASUPRA SERVICIILOR DE ÎNVĂȚĂMÂNTUL SUPERIOR (STUDIUL DE CAZ AL ISRAELULUI ȘI MOLDOVEI)

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***Rezumat:** Tendințele de creștere a cererii în rândul studenților din sistemele de învățământ superior conduc la îmbunătățirea accesibilității și a confortului, costuri mai mici și aplicarea directă a conținutului în mediile de lucru din institute. Aceasta schimbă radical mediul local și internațional pentru sistemul de învățământ superior. Noul fenomen de utilizare a metodelor tehnice este cererea concurenței între organizație. Dacă ne uităm la Statele Unite și la nivel global (alte țări), în acest mediu în schimbare rapidă, care se bazează din ce în ce mai mult în contextul unei economii globale și bazate pe cunoaștere și al competiției dintre sistemele de învățământ superior. Autorul a constatat că organizațiile învățământului superior din Israel și Moldova au suferit schimbări, iar noile evoluții sunt*

alimentate de progresele accelerate. Autorul va descrie situația locală și tendințele din sistemul de învățământ superior israelian și moldovenesc.

***Cuvinte cheie:** concurență, sistemul serviciilor educaționale, organizație de excelență, învățământ superior.*

1. Introduction

The trends of growing demand among learners in higher education systems leading for improved accessibility and convenience, lower costs, and direct application of content to work settings in the institutes. This radically changing the local and international environment for higher education system. The new phenomenon of using technical methods are demand the competition between the organization. If we look at the United States and globally (other countries), in this rapidly changing environment, which is increasingly based within the context of a global and knowledge-based economy and competition between higher education systems. Some of traditional universities are attempting to adapt purposes, structures, and programs, and new organizations are emerging in response. The author found that higher education organizational in Israel and Moldova have changes, and new developments are being fueled by accelerating advances. It takes place in digital communications and learning technologies that are sweeping the world, especially on that time of the Corona Virus (Covid-19). The growing demand for learning, making research, having an open academic discourse, practices of models combined with these technical advances, is in fact a critical pressure point for challenging the dominant assumptions and characteristics of existing traditionally organized universities in the 21st century.

2. Main materials

Competitiveness in higher education. The contemporary higher education market is characterized in multiple and dynamic changes, and requires all the commercial companies and the institutes, including higher education institutes, to develop fast and flexible reactions in order to survive and develop their competition abilities in the market they operate in. Some of the noticeable economic-educational changes are related to the economic – social reality and to the public sector financial means. Therefore, the considerations become more financial and based on organizational – economic benefits. One of the subjects that make increasing scientific – research interest is the competitiveness in higher education. According to Bao [1], the society development in the aspect of economic knowledge in the 21st century is characterized in expending the knowledge limits, shortening the knowledge "circle of life" and the appearance of new knowledge in

a very fast pace. Therefore, learning become a long process of many years that not really ever ends in most occupational professions. At the same time, there is an increasing competition between the higher education service suppliers since it is a privatized market, and the economic reality of countries does not enable increased budget of pedagogic and administrative needs of the higher education institutes. It was found that many of the institutes are looking for "the formula" how to enrich the university in order to attract more students and maintain organizational and pedagogic attractiveness to the target audience – the students. In these circumstances, the service quality of higher education institutes becomes the "key word" for service suppliers. The researcher has found that the more developed the country, the more it emphasizes education and its role in economic and social development. In addition, it was found in her research, that those who benefit the education service constantly examine and evaluate its quality. According to Toquero [11], it may be said that the competitiveness level between institutes set challenges, policy and high expectations from the quality service of education.

Moreover, the economic and cultural globalization, which influenced the academic establishment in each country created new challenges to the higher education system since it obligates global openness and knowledge exchange. It all happens since the labor market becomes an increasing liberalization of knowledge itself. Due to Levzion [8], to create a competitive market position for higher education institute in these circumstances, it has to adopt marketing concept and philosophy and create its strategy and activity in the market performance terms: to focus on the beneficiaries needs, in market segmentation, competition, market location and product development / new services based on identified market trends. One of the significant examples to this economic – survival need is the reaction of academic institutes to the required changes during the COVID -19 pandemic outbreak.

The influence of COVID-19 virus on higher education. Following the outbreak of COVID-19 virus all over the world education systems, starting with elementary schools up to the higher education institutes, have moved to distance teaching and learning. Each country has formulated its policy regarding learning due to its abilities, budgets, available technology and communication with the students. The option to offer academic leaning through online distance learning is not strange to academic institutes in most of the institutes and countries. the term MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) is known for many years, but until recently most of studies in higher education institutes were conducted by the traditional form through frontal teaching, while various technologic means used to support teaching [10]. Now, when everybody understood the pandemic is here to stay,

academic institutes begun to promote competitiveness that is based on providing solutions to the need (frontal teaching is not allowed) and develop distance learning as part of marketing the academic organization. Distance learning has clear advantages and disadvantages. Among the advantages we may find:

1. Increasing the accessibility of knowledge and learning.
2. Reducing the academic leaning costs.
3. Strengthening the competitiveness and development of academic teaching.
4. Improved measurement of learning processes and course management and strengthening the link and compatibility between academic studies and the labor market.

Among the disadvantages we may find:

1. The fear of diminishing the "market value" of an academic degree.
2. Fear of deteriorating of online studies quality
3. Reduction of student – lecturer dialog, the academic experience and the system supporting the student and limitation of the ability to evaluate the students' academic level.

In addition to the detailed disadvantages, we may also mention the inability to conduct practical workshops that are, in some cases, part of the curriculum academic requirements and the difficulty of weak students or disabled students to cope with the challenge of distance learning.

The transition to distance learning and teaching have set significant technologic challenge to the academic institutes. First and foremost, the technological platforms institutes used were forced to cope with significant increase in the number of lecturers and students using it simultaneously. In addition, students and lecturers, who were not accustomed to use distance learning were forced to buy suitable computing equipment and learn to operate the systems. The teaching staff at the academic institutions indeed engaged the task and within a short time the entire higher education system moved to distance teaching and learning.

The competitiveness in higher education in Israel. The universities in Israel have finally understood in the last years (2015-2020) they must fight for their existence and begun to develop marketing systems, knowledge centers and telemarketing – like the colleges. They have also started in massive advertising campaigns that include open days and suggestions that students have were never received before. In addition, universities have lowered the acceptance terms for various faculties and opened pre-academic preparatory studies in diverse subjects, especially in the fields of sciences.

Levzion [8] even notes that during the time universities have looked the other side, colleges have managed to be legitimized in the academic market and produce many gradulators that have integrated in industry, some in key positions and leading management roles. The "qualitative" target audience – who have high grades in his psychometric and matriculation exams – does not automatically chose the university in Israel as his first choice, but examines what leading colleges have to offer. Donitsa-Schmidt [6] adds that colleges are open to think outside the box and to academic flexibility, efficient and quick service systems, active occupational directions, and the most important – professional and hungry presidents, CEOs and marketing managers, who have wide marketing experience in the target audience. According to CHE [4], some of the colleges even made this year (2020) a marketing leap after assimilating advanced database management systems in their information centers, which allow managing multiple advertising channels with result component.

Improving the competitiveness between higher education institutes in Israel during the "COVID-19 time". There is wide consent in higher education in Israel in one subject: the higher education campus after the COVID-19 crisis will not look the same as it looked before. The worldwide experiment conducted this year in distance academic studies will dramatically change the academic degree. Within a week and a half since the institutes' campuses in Israel were closed, by the middle of March, all the higher education institutes moved to full or almost full distance academic studies. everybody prepared to the option they will have to finish the semester without having the students meeting face to face with their lecturers even once and no one doubts this is possible. The article editor found that the institutes compete each other of having various platforms and integrating suitable technology to attract many students to their institute. They believe, the idea that the student will gain a quality teaching through distance learning attracts the Israeli student.

According to Levzion [8], **the universities knew for years they have to be prepared for a new era of competitiveness that include much more than online learning. But the lecturers and the institutions too felt comfortable to continue doing what they know and the transition to digital was slow or even not at all.** Now, the lecturers were obligated to learn the technology fast, because if they will not do so, there will be a buzz by the student side that will harm the competitive reputation of the institution.

When the COVID-19 crisis will be over everyone will already know how to teach using Zoom. The president of the Hebrew University in Jerusalem, Prof. Asher Cohen, was proud they have increased from 30 online courses to 3,000

within a week. The Technion in Haifa and the Open University leaped in the number of online courses and almost all the courses of these institutes are available in distance learning. In order to understand the competitive lever led by the COVID-19 pandemic, the article editor will present in figure 1.1 the increase in online courses supply of four higher education institutes in Israel.

Figure 1. Number of Mooc/ Zoom courses in Israeli Universities before Corona virus & 2020-21 academic year

Source: made by the author from source [5]

This article's editor sees a clear trend, through the data in figure 1.1, which shows that the academic institutes are interested in maintaining their relative advantage and therefore offer a large number of courses using technologic means. The competitiveness between higher education institutes in Israel is clear and institutions seem to understand that dependence on government budgets declining every year. There is no doubt that the board of directors of any university or college has a very significant decision to make.

Higher education in Moldova. The competitiveness and internationality of higher education in Moldova, like in other countries, entered the agenda and high priority in many universities. The universities in Moldova focus today in creating international relations, in developing internationality channel – student mobility, and developing innovative and attractive curricula for an integrated student audience (local and international). The universities strive to invest human and economic resources to prepare their gradulators to cope with worldwide challenges, and to open for them option of globalized training and employment. The globalization and perceptual independence, after the Soviet rule period, promoted thinking and management patterns of openness to international education strategies and new approaches to managing international activity. Moldova was also caught

unprepared by the COVID-19 pandemic and, at the beginning, as in most countries, its implication was not understood.

With the pandemic onset in March the studies were stopped and became online through correspondence and Zoom classes. The problem academic institutes are facing is the limited abilities of the technologic system. Like in Israel, the institutes are not prepared to apply distance learning, therefore they have postponed the academic year opening until a new date that will be decided. The European Union, through the ERASMUS program, published a report called "*Overview of the higher education system*" regarding the academic establishment in Moldova in which the current status for this year (2017) is presented.

The report addressed also to the problematic structures in the higher education management and the ways to improve it. The World Bank recently (September 2019) donated millions of dollars to stabilize the state educational system and upgrade the academic institutes. As part of the planned improvements the technologic infrastructure will be improved, the budgeting system of institutes will be improved, contemporary contents and courses will be integrated, and distance learning teaching infrastructure will be established. In addition, the Moldavian government has started to take actions that will strengthen the competitive ability of the local institutes:

1. **Developing national strategy in the higher education establishment** – according to the national education perception of the government in Moldova, lifelong learning includes learning activities a person performs during his in order to build or develop abilities from a personal, civic, social and professional point of view.

2. **The higher education reconstruction** – by decision, in order to preserve the competitiveness of higher education institutions in the country, higher education is accessible for all those who holds a matriculation diploma (national or international). The local citizens will get higher education for free and it will be funded by the state. Each Moldavian citizen deserves a free of charge first degree.

3. **Internationalism of the institutes** – Moldova joined in 2005 to the Bologna reform. Starting this process, the Republic of Moldova have accepted the responsibility and was actively involved in the reform and modernization process of higher education, in order to meet the European standards. The first changes caused a change in the university system structure, organization of higher education in three cycles – establishment of ECTS studies. after adopting the new international education line, several changes were performed in higher education in Moldova, aimed to renew the system and match the European standards. These changes include developing new university curricula or organizing the internal and

external quality evaluation and supervision system by establishing the national agency of quality assurance in vocational education.

The republic of Moldova understood that strengthening its internationality will strengthen its competitiveness in comparison to most East European countries. figure 1.2 shows the increase in the number of international students in the State of Moldova in recent years.

Figure 2. The number of International students in Moldova 2013 -2019.

Source: made by the author from [8]

The article editor understands from the graph data that the Moldavian government acts very efficiently to increase the number of international students, an action that will lead to international success and increase of the academic institutes' competitiveness comparing to other countries.

3. Conclusions:

The research editor distinguishes two different directions of competitive creation in higher education of each country. There is no doubt that the recent time extreme changes, including the COVID-19 pandemic influence, bring the academic establishment in each country to take creative actions to preserve the academic institute reputation and its ability to confront marketing competition with other institutes, or as in the reality of the higher education in Moldova, with other countries. The higher education in Israel expresses the competitions between the institutes themselves, but there is no real reinforcement to the international student issue. However, the higher education in Moldova keeps reinforcing the external competitiveness, i.e. in comparison to higher education in other country.

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